

Community Satisfaction of Community Development Program: A Case Study of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA Program in West Bangka

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ABSTRACT: The MENJAGA NUSANTARA (Mentok Berjaya dan Bahagia Melalui Inklusifitas Berkelanjutan dan Sejahtera) program is one of the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives implemented by PT Timah Tbk Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok, focusing on community empowerment in Belo Laut Village, Air Putih Village, Tanjung Subdistrict, and Sungai Baru Subdistrict. To assess its effectiveness, a Community Satisfaction Index (CSI) survey was conducted involving 75 program recipients. This study aims to measure the level of community satisfaction with the program's implementation and to identify aspects that require further strengthening for future development. A descriptive quantitative approach was employed using a Likert-scale questionnaire (1–4), covering four key aspects: program implementation, program management, program distribution, and service quality. The data were analyzed by calculating the CSI score for each aspect, which was then converted into a 100-point index. The results indicate that the overall CSI score reached 3.425 with a converted index of 85.625, classified as very satisfactory. By aspect, program implementation scored 3.367 (84.167), program management 3.495 (87.375), program distribution 3.413 (85.333), and service quality 3.425 (85.625), all within the very satisfactory category. Recipients highlighted the relevance, benefits, sustainability, participation, synergy, facilitator performance, accuracy of targeting, and responsiveness as strong points of the program. In conclusion, the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program is considered successful in enhancing community capacity and shows strong prospects for sustainability. Recipients expressed their hope for the program's continuation, complemented by additional training in human resource development, to enable its evolution into an independent and sustainable community-based enterprise.

KEYWORDS: Community Satisfaction Index, Corporate Social Responsibility, PT Timah Tbk, Community Empowerment, Program Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Community empowerment programs are an important strategy in realizing sustainable development, especially in areas around the company (Halimah et al., 2024). The implementation of the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) serves not only as a form of compliance with regulations, but also as a means to improve the quality of life of the community, strengthen relationships with stakeholders, and maintain the sustainability of the company's business (Arsyad et al., 2017; Rahmadani et al., 2019). The legal basis for implementing CSR in Indonesia is regulated in Undang-Undang Nomor 40 Tahun 2007 tentang Perseroan Terbatas Pasal 74, and reinforced by Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 47 Tahun 2012 tentang Tanggung Jawab Sosial dan Lingkungan Perseroan Terbatas which requires companies operating in the natural resources sector to implement social and environmental responsibility. The regulation affirms that CSR is not only a form of legal compliance, but also part of efforts to create a balance between the interests of business, society, and the environment (Samino et al., 2024). CSR has also been widely recognized as a strategic tool to enhance corporate legitimacy and contribute to sustainable development (Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Jamali & Karam, 2016).

To assess the effectiveness of the implementation of CSR programs, an evaluation instrument is needed that can provide an objective picture of community acceptance of the program being run (Kusbudiyanto et al., 2023). Community Satisfaction Index (CSI) is one measure that can be used to determine the level of satisfaction of beneficiaries to the quality of service of a program (Sigit, 2022). CSI measurement results can be the basis for companies to assess the extent to which CSR programs have been running as expected and provide sustainable benefits (Kusbudiyanto et al., 2023).

Previous studies have shown the importance of measuring the CSI in CSR programs. Research Muhamad et al. (2023) the CSR program of PT Solusi Bangun Indonesia in Tuban showed a high level of satisfaction with water management programs and

productive economic development. Similarly, a study by Sigit (2022) confirms that CSI can be used as indicators of CSR success in encouraging community independence. However, some research still focuses on the agricultural, environmental, or public service sectors. Studies on community satisfaction with CSR programs in the mining and mineral processing sector, particularly in coastal areas, remain relatively limited. Furthermore, the measurement of CSI in this study is not only conducted on general aspects but also covers management, distribution, and service dimensions of the program.

Accordingly, a CSI survey was conducted to assess the satisfaction level of recipients of PT TIMAH Tbk's Community Development Program in Belo Laut Village, Air Putih Village, Tanjung Subdistrict, and Sungai Baru Subdistrict, West Bangka Regency. The results of this survey are expected to provide an overview of community satisfaction as recipients of the program.

METHODS

A. Data Collection

A public satisfaction survey for the MENJAGA NUSANTARA (Mentok Berjaya dan Bahagia Melalui Inklusifitas Berkelanjutan dan Sejahtera) program was conducted in August 2025 in four target areas: Belo Laut Village, Air Putih Village, Tanjung Subdistrict, and Sungai Baru Subdistrict in West Bangka Regency. The study involved 75 respondents, all of whom were direct recipients of the program, selected representing the proportion of each region.

The research tool consisted of a questionnaire that included closed and open-ended questions. The closed questions were designed to measure the CSI using a 4-point Likert Scale, where 1 = not satisfied, 2 = less satisfied, 3 = satisfied, and 4 = very satisfied. The Likert scale was chosen because it is widely recognized as an effective tool for measuring attitudes, perceptions, and level of satisfaction in social research (Suwandi et al., 2018). This scale simplifies the choice of respondents, ensures consistency in answers, and provides quantitative data for further analysis (Kusbudiyanto et al., 2023; Setyawan & Atapukan, 2008). Open-ended questions are included to gather qualitative feedback such as expectations, criticisms, and suggestions (Sabilah & Manoy, 2018). Data collection was conducted through face-to-face interviews to ensure clear understanding by respondents.

B. Data Analysis

The collected survey data is processed using Microsoft Excel before calculating the CSI (Izmaya & Purnamasari, 2021). Data will be processed to obtain CSI in the following ways:

1. Calculating the average score per question by dividing the total score for each question by the number of questionnaires completed:

$$\text{Average score per question} = \frac{\text{Total Score per question}}{\text{Number of completed questionnaires}}$$

2. Define a weight for each question, calculated as one divided by the total number of questions.

$$\text{Weight} = \frac{1}{\text{Total number of questions}}$$

3. Calculating the weighted average score per question, obtained by multiplying the average score of each question by its weight.

$$\text{Weighted average score} = \text{Average score per question} \times \text{Weight}$$

4. Calculating the converted CSI, which is the sum of all weighted average scores multiplied by the conversion factor of 25.

$$\text{Converted CSI} = (\sum \text{Weighted average scores}) \times 25$$

5. Interpreting the CSI score based on service quality categories.

The interpretation of the converted CSI scores is presented in the following table:

Table 1 Interpretation of Community Satisfaction Index Scores

No	Converted Community Satisfaction Index Score	Description
1	0 – 25	Not Satisfied
2	26 – 50	Less Satisfied
3	51 – 75	Satisfied
4	76 – 100	Very Satisfied

The processed data were further analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative analysis was presented in the form of tables and graphs, illustrating the distribution of CSI scores across different aspects and the overall results. Qualitative analysis was carried out in a descriptive form, elaborating on respondents’ feedback regarding program relevance, benefits, participation, and expectations for sustainability. This combined presentation ensures that the research findings not only demonstrate statistical outcomes but also provide deeper insights into community perceptions of the CSR program.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondent Profile

Table 2 Characteristics of Respondents to the MENJAGA NUSANTARA Program

Category	Sub-Category	Number (people)	Percentage (%)
Age	<25 years	10	13
	26–45 years	26	35
	46–65 years	39	52
Education	No formal education	4	5
	Elementary School	16	21
	Junior High School	25	33
	Senior High School	18	24
	Diploma	12	16
	Occupation	Entrepreneur	6
	Farmer/Fisherman	11	15
	Laborer	9	12
	Housewife	8	11
	Daily worker	6	8
	Private employee	18	24
	Unemployed	17	23
Income	< Rp1,000,000	41	55
	Rp1,000,000–3,000,000	31	41
	Rp3,000,000–5,000,000	3	4

The respondents in this study consisted of 75 recipients of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program. Based on their characteristics, the majority were in the 46–65 years age group (52%), with the largest educational background being junior high school (33%) and senior high school/vocational school (24%). Most respondents worked in the informal sector, such as farmers/fishermen, laborers, and private employees, while 23% were unemployed or without permanent jobs. In terms of income, more than half of the respondents (55%) earned less than Rp1,000,000 per month. These findings indicate that the program’s target group is predominantly composed of communities with vulnerable socio-economic conditions, making the company’s CSR intervention highly relevant to improving their welfare.

B. Community Satisfaction Index

The Community Satisfaction Index is a value or level used to measure community. To assess the community satisfaction index, this survey uses a Likert scale. The scoring method uses a scale of 1 to 4. Further analysis converts this to a scale of 100 (Setyawan & Atapukan, 2008)

The satisfaction index of the recipients of this community empowerment program was calculated for three aspects, namely the overall program, program management, and program distribution and service. The total community satisfaction index and the community satisfaction index for each aspect are as follows:

1. Overall Community Satisfaction Index of the Program

The community satisfaction index for the overall program was measured based on the program’s relevance to community needs in relation to existing problems and local potential, the benefits of the program, and its sustainability. The survey results regarding the relevance of the program to community needs in terms of issues and potential can be seen in the following diagram:

Figure 1 Diagram of Program Relevance

Table 3 Respondents’ Perceptions of the Benefits of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA Program

Program Benefit Element	Score 1 (No Improvement)	Score 2 (Slight Improvement)	Score 3 (Improved)	Score 4 (Highly Improved)
Knowledge enhancement	0%	0%	52%	48%
Skills improvement	0%	4%	49%	47%
Environmental quality improvement	0%	0%	36%	64%
Community income improvement	0%	1%	71%	28%

Based on Table 3, the most significant benefit of the program was reflected in the improvement of environmental quality, where 64% of respondents stated they were very satisfied and 36% reported being satisfied. This indicates that the program has succeeded in generating a tangible positive impact on the community’s environmental conditions.

The knowledge enhancement aspect also received high appreciation, with 52% of respondents expressing satisfaction and 48% reporting very satisfied. These results suggest that the program has been effective in providing relevant knowledge and insights for the beneficiary communities.

In terms of skills improvement, the majority of respondents reported being satisfied (49%) and very satisfied (47%), although 4% indicated less satisfaction. This finding highlights that the program has been fairly successful in strengthening community skills, though a small proportion of recipients still perceived that the benefits were not fully optimal.

For the income improvement aspect, the responses were dominated by satisfied (71%), followed by very satisfied (28%), with 1% reporting less satisfied. This distribution illustrates that while the program has contributed to enhancing community income, the economic benefits were not perceived as maximized compared to the achievements in other aspects.

Beyond program relevance and benefits, the overall CSI also considered the sustainability of the program. Sustainability was analyzed in terms of the continuity of activities provided and the commitment of the community to maintain and independently continue the program after being handed over by PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting Mentok.

Figure 2 Community Perceptions of Program Sustainability

Figure 3 Respondents' Readiness to Continue the Program Without PT TIMAH Tbk's Assistance

The survey results presented in Figure 2 show that the sustainability aspect of the program received a positive assessment from the community, with 67% of respondents stating that the program is sustainable and 33% indicating that it is highly sustainable. This strong appreciation is consistent with the community's readiness to implement the program independently, as illustrated in Figure 3, where 64% of respondents reported being ready, 35% very ready, and only 1% less ready.

This condition indicates that the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program is not only perceived as relevant in the short term, but also has the potential for sustainability through community initiatives in developing and disseminating the knowledge and skills acquired to families and the surrounding environment. This is reflected in the willingness of the community to continue to develop and disseminate the knowledge and skills gained from the program to their families and surrounding communities.

The results of data processing related to the survey results on the relevance of the program, the benefits of the program, and the sustainability of the program to produce a CSI for the overall program of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program are as follows:

Table 4 Community Satisfaction Index Value

Index Value	Converted CSI	Interpretation
3.367	84.167	Very Satisfactory

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the CSI for the program as a whole reached a score of 3.367, with a converted index value of 84.167, which falls into the very satisfactory category. This shows that the relevance, benefits, and sustainability of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program are evaluated very positively by the beneficiary community.

The high level of satisfaction shows that the program implemented by PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok, not only meets the needs of the community but also provides tangible benefits in terms of knowledge, skills, environmental quality, and economic welfare. In addition, a strong appreciation for the sustainability of the program reflects the community's belief that the initiative will continue to operate and generate long-term positive impacts.

Thus, this CSR program has succeeded in building community trust and support.

2. Community Satisfaction Index on Program Management

The CSI of the recipients of this community empowerment program is calculated for three aspects, namely the overall program, program management, and program distribution and services. The results of the survey related to public participation in the planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation stages of the program are presented in the following table:

Table 5 Community Participation in the Program

Community Participation Aspect	Not Good	Less Good	Good	Very Good
Planning	0%	4%	51%	45%
Implementation	0%	0%	41%	59%
Monitoring and Evaluation	0%	11%	41%	48%

Based on Table 5, most respondents considered that the efforts of community involvement in the CSR program of PT TIMAH Tbk were implemented well to very well. At the planning stage, 51% of respondents stated good, 45% very good, and only 4% rated less good. During the program implementation stage, 41% rated good and 59% very good, while in the monitoring and evaluation stage, 48% stated very good, 41% good, and 11% less good. These results show that people consider their level of involvement in the program to be quite high, although a small percentage still feel not fully involved in the evaluation process.

In addition, the stakeholder synergy element received a positive assessment, with 47% of respondents rating it good and 53% rating it very good. This shows that PT TIMAH Tbk has successfully built communication and collaboration with various local stakeholders throughout all stages of the program. Meanwhile, the performance of CSR facilitators is also considered good to very good, especially in terms of proximity to the community, adaptability, accountability, and competence in the field.

These findings show that PT TIMAH Tbk's CSR program management has been implemented effectively through community participation, stakeholder synergy, and the support of competent facilitators. This is in line with the concept of community involvement, which highlighted the importance of active community participation in fostering a sense of ownership of the program. While positive assessments of facilitators highlight the importance of professional human resources in bridging the gap between companies and communities (Wibisono, 2007).

Therefore, program management aspects are not only considered excellent but also form a fundamental basis for the sustainability of community empowerment initiatives. The results of the survey on CSR facilitator performance are presented in the following table:

Table 6 Performance of Facilitators/CDO

Facilitator/CDO Performance Aspect	Not Good	Less Good	Good	Very Good
Closeness to the community	0%	0%	47%	53%
Adaptability	0%	0%	51%	49%
Responsibility	0%	0%	44%	56%
Competence	0%	0%	53%	47%

Based on Table 6, most respondents rated the performance of PT TIMAH Tbk's CSR facilitators as very good. A total of 47% of respondents stated that the facilitator were close to the community and 53% stated that they were very close, which was indicated by the recognition of all respondents that they knew the facilitators well. In terms of adaptability, 51% of respondents rated it good and 49% rated it very good, indicating that the facilitator was able to be well received by the community.

Furthermore, the responsibility element received an assessment of 44% good and 56% very good, showing public confidence in the seriousness of the facilitator in implementing the program. In the aspect of technical competence, 47% of respondents rated it good and 53% very good, indicating that the facilitator is considered capable of organizing the program as well as solving problems that arise in the field.

This result shows that the performance of CSR facilitator PT TIMAH Tbk is positively assessed by the community, both in terms of social closeness, adaptability, responsibility, and technical competence. This finding confirms the importance of the role of professional and adaptive human resources in supporting the success of CSR program management, as stated by Wibisono (2007) that the quality of facilitators is a key factor in bridging companies with beneficiary communities.

The results of data processing related to survey results on community participation, synergy, and facilitator performance or CSR resulted in a CSI for program management from the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program are as follows:

Table 7 Community Satisfaction Index for Program Management

Index Value	Converted CSI	Interpretation
3.495	87.375	Very Satisfactory

Based on Table 7, the value of the CSI for the management aspect of the program is 3.495, with a converted index of 87.375 or in the category of very satisfied. This result shows that elements of community participation, synergy with stakeholders, and the performance of facilitators or CSR are considered very good by program recipients.

The high appreciation of the community in this aspect indicates that the management of PT TIMAH Tbk'S CSR program has been implemented effectively, both in encouraging community involvement at every stage of the activity, establishing communication and cooperation with local stakeholders, as well as through the role of adaptive, responsible and competent facilitators in the field.

3. Community Satisfaction Index on Program Delivery and Services

The community satisfaction index for program delivery and services was measured using four indicators: accuracy and clarity of the method or program, reliability of the method or program, fairness, and responsiveness. The survey results regarding community assessments of the accuracy and clarity of the method or program are presented in the following diagram:

Figure 4 Accuracy and Clarity of the Method or Program

Based on Figure 4, 3% of respondents assessed that the program delivery was less appropriate to the conditions of the target community, while 37% considered it appropriate and 60% rated it as highly appropriate. This indicates that the majority of respondents perceived the program implemented by PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, through MENJAGA NUSANTARA (Mentok Berjaya dan Bahagia Melalui Inklusifitas Berkelanjutan dan Sejahtera) program, as accurate and relevant to community needs. In addition, the reliability aspect of the program was rated highly, with 81% of respondents considering it reliable and 19% very reliable.

For the fairness aspect, measured through the accuracy of targeting and equity in beneficiary distribution, 39% of respondents rated it appropriate and 61% very appropriate. This demonstrates that the distribution of the program was considered fair and capable of reaching the groups entitled to receive benefits. Meanwhile, in terms of responsiveness, PT TIMAH Tbk's response to criticism, input, and suggestions was assessed positively, with 55% of respondents rating it good and 45% very good, indicating the existence of a two-way communication mechanism between the company and beneficiary communities.

Overall, these results prove that the implementation of PT TIMAH Tbk's CSR program is considered very good in terms of accuracy, fairness, reliability, and responsiveness. It also reflects the company's commitment in ensuring transparency and accountability at every stage of program implementation.

The survey Data processed related to the accuracy and clarity of the method or program, reliability, fairness, and responsiveness resulted in the CSI for the implementation of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program and services as follows:

Table 8 Community Satisfaction Index for Program Delivery and Services

Index Value	Converted CSI	Interpretation
3.413	85.333	Very Satisfactory

Based on Table 8, the CSI score for the program delivery aspect was 3.413, with a converted index value of 85.333, which falls into the very satisfactory category. This result indicates that the accuracy of the program methods, reliability, fairness in the distribution of benefits, as well as responsiveness to input and criticism, are all rated very well by the recipients of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program.

The high level of community appreciation reflects that PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok, has carried out the program delivery process in a transparent and accountable manner, while also being able to meet the needs and expectations of the target communities.

4. Total Community Satisfaction Index

The calculation results of the total or overall CSI for the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program, as part of the community development initiatives of PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok, are presented in the following table:

Table 9 Total Community Satisfaction Index

Index Value	Converted CSI	Interpretation
3.425	85.625	Very Satisfactory

Based on Table 9, the total CSI score of the MENJAGA NUSANTARA program was 3.425, with a converted index value of 85.625, which falls into the very satisfactory category. This result indicates that, overall, the program implementation was assessed as very good by the beneficiary communities.

In addition to expressing appreciation, the community also conveyed their expectations that PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok, would continue this empowerment program until the community is fully capable of developing it into an independent and sustainable business entity. The primary expectation of the recipients is the enhancement of capacity in managing the existing program, along with additional training in the field of sustainable human resource development. Thus, the program is expected not only to provide immediate impact but also to strengthen the foundation of the community's economic and social independence in the long term.

C. Conclusion

The MENJAGA NUSANTARA program implemented by PT TIMAH Tbk, Division of Processing and Smelting, Mentok achieved a total CSI score of 3.425 with a converted value of 85.625, categorized as "very satisfactory." This indicates that the aspects of management, delivery, benefits, and sustainability were highly valued by the community, reflecting the program's tangible contributions to improving knowledge, skills, environmental quality, and economic well-being in a sustainable manner.

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